

Fig. B.1: S/N extracted from the FITS header of the spectra on the order that contains the sodium feature (*left panels*) and airmass (*right panel*) measured for each target of our sample. Vertical continuous lines indicate the points of first and fourth contact of the transit, while vertical dashed lines represent the points of second and third contact.

Table B.5: Summary of the best-fit parameters and 1- σ error bars obtained with the MCMC fitting procedure for WASP-69 b.

WASP-69 b								
		$c D_2$ [%]	$c D_1$ [%]	$f_{D2/D1}$	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{wind} [km s ⁻¹]	r [R_p]	K_p [km s ⁻¹]
W69-N1	2016-06-03	-6.58 ^{+1.60} _{-1.89}	-0.65 ^{+0.46} _{-0.81}	10 ⁺²⁵ ₋₆	3.9 ^{+1.6} _{-1.1}	-0.0 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	0.98 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	125.0 ^{+8.7} _{-8.9}
W69-N2	2016-08-04	-3.14 ^{+1.75} _{-6.12}	-2.76 ^{+1.73} _{-8.88}	1.13 ^{+1.63} _{-0.69}	3.9 ^{+6.7} _{-3.5}	-5.4 ^{+2.5} _{-4.1}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	128.0 ^{+10.7} _{-10.5}
W69-N3	2019-07-23	-1.57 ^{+0.36} _{-0.42}	-0.82 ^{+0.23} _{-0.25}	1.9 ^{+0.8} _{-0.5}	37.8 ^{+11.1} _{-8.1}	-7.8 ^{+2.7} _{-3.2}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	124.1 ^{+10.0} _{-9.8}
W69-N4	2020-08-09	-4.21 ^{+3.73} _{-7.39}	-0.70 ^{+0.54} _{-3.19}	3.3 ^{+13.8} _{-2.5}	1.1 ^{+23.6} _{-0.8}	+0.7 ^{+12.9} _{-2.3}	1.01 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	122.8 ^{+12.6} _{-12.2}
W69-N5	2023-07-28	-2.11 ^{+1.44} _{-2.57}	-0.91 ^{+0.58} _{-1.30}	1.8 ^{+3.6} _{-1.0}	2.4 ^{+9.5} _{-1.7}	+10.4 ^{+1.0} _{-4.4}	0.97 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	124.5 ^{+8.8} _{-10.9}
W69-N6	2024-07-14	-0.86 ^{+0.36} _{-0.38}	-1.22 ^{+0.37} _{-0.41}	0.71 ^{+0.41} _{-0.30}	16.2 ^{+4.8} _{-4.0}	-5.8 ^{+2.4} _{-2.6}	1.01 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	127.1 ^{+9.6} _{-9.8}
All nights		-0.94 ^{+0.20} _{-0.23}	-0.51 ^{+0.15} _{-0.15}	1.8 ^{+0.8} _{-0.5}	19.7 ^{+4.5} _{-3.4}	-1.4 ^{+1.5} _{-1.5}	0.98 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	124.8 ^{+10.3} _{-10.2}
W69-N1+N2+N3+N6		-1.45 ^{+0.25} _{-0.25}	-0.89 ^{+0.20} _{-0.22}	1.6 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	18.8 ^{+3.1} _{-2.5}	-4.8 ^{+1.3} _{-1.3}	0.99 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	127.0 ^{+9.7} _{-9.9}

Table B.6: Summary of the best-fit parameters and 1- σ error bars obtained with the MCMC fitting procedure for WASP-76 b.

WASP-76 b								
		$c D_2$ [%]	$c D_1$ [%]	$f_{D2/D1}$	FWHM [km s ⁻¹]	v_{wind} [km s ⁻¹]	r [R_p]	K_p [km s ⁻¹]
W76-N1	2012-11-11	-0.62 ^{+0.14} _{-0.16}	-0.63 ^{+0.14} _{-0.15}	0.99 ^{+0.32} _{-0.25}	31.6 ^{+8.3} _{-6.7}	-4.2 ^{+3.1} _{-2.8}	0.95 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	185.8 ^{+10.2} _{-9.9}
W76-N2	2017-10-24	-0.56 ^{+0.10} _{-0.11}	-0.49 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	1.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.2}	44.5 ^{+9.3} _{-7.9}	-8.2 ^{+3.0} _{-3.2}	0.96 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	197.0 ^{+9.1} _{-9.2}
W76-N3	2017-10-26	-0.30 ^{+0.22} _{-0.49}	-1.20 ^{+0.50} _{-0.83}	0.3 ^{+0.4} _{-0.2}	15.1 ^{+14.4} _{-9.0}	-17.1 ^{+4.5} _{-3.2}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	198.6 ^{+10.6} _{-9.2}
W76-N4	2017-11-22	-0.39 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	-0.57 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}	0.69 ^{+0.19} _{-0.16}	27.2 ^{+5.3} _{-4.5}	-3.0 ^{+1.9} _{-1.8}	0.97 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	199.8 ^{+8.6} _{-8.9}
W76-N5	2018-10-12	-0.52 ^{+0.19} _{-0.29}	-0.17 ^{+0.12} _{-0.25}	3.0 ^{+5.9} _{-1.6}	10.9 ^{+7.9} _{-6.3}	-4.1 ^{+3.1} _{-2.3}	0.98 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	193.8 ^{+10.6} _{-8.9}
W76-N6	2018-11-01	-19.1 ^{+1.63} _{-0.66}	-6.12 ^{+4.79} _{-8.48}	2.71 ^{+9.13} _{-1.52}	0.1 ^{+0.1} _{-0.0}	-8.8 ^{+1.5} _{-0.9}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	194.6 ^{+7.0} _{-10.5}
W76-N7	2018-11-30	-0.69 ^{+0.16} _{-0.19}	-0.35 ^{+0.14} _{-0.15}	2.0 ^{+1.3} _{-0.6}	13.8 ^{+5.3} _{-4.1}	-5.1 ^{+1.4} _{-1.6}	0.99 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	193.4 ^{+6.6} _{-6.8}
W76-N8	2019-11-27	-0.62 ^{+0.19} _{-0.19}	-0.53 ^{+0.14} _{-0.17}	1.1 ^{+0.3} _{-0.3}	41.8 ^{+38.3} _{-12.5}	-1.4 ^{+3.3} _{-3.6}	0.98 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	202.1 ^{+9.3} _{-9.2}
W76-N9	2023-11-03	-0.51 ^{+0.12} _{-0.13}	-0.39 ^{+0.11} _{-0.12}	1.3 ^{+0.7} _{-0.4}	17.5 ^{+4.6} _{-3.7}	-5.1 ^{+2.0} _{-2.1}	0.94 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	195.2 ^{+8.9} _{-9.5}
All nights		-0.52 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	-0.43 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	1.2 ^{+0.1} _{-0.1}	22.2 ^{+2.0} _{-1.8}	-4.5 ^{+0.8} _{-0.8}	0.84 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	197.3 ^{+5.3} _{-5.5}
W76-N1+N2+N3+N4+N5+N7+N8+N9		-0.52 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	-0.43 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	1.2 ^{+0.2} _{-0.1}	22.3 ^{+2.0} _{-1.9}	-4.5 ^{+0.8} _{-0.8}	0.83 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	197.4 ^{+5.4} _{-5.4}

Table B.7: Summary of the best-fit parameters and $1-\sigma$ error bars obtained with the MCMC fitting procedure for HD 209458 b.

HD 209458 b							
		$c D_2$	$c D_1$	FWHM	v_{wind}	r	K_p
		[%]	[%]	[km s ⁻¹]	[km s ⁻¹]	[R _p]	[km s ⁻¹]
HD2-N1	2015-09-26	-0.02 ^{+8.65} _{-5.32}	-5.79 ^{+5.49} _{-6.51}	0.1 ^{+15.2} _{-0.0}	+4.4 ^{+1.4} _{-0.1}	0.99 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	140.6 ^{+13.7} _{-5.7}
HD2-N2	2016-09-16	+5.60 ^{+6.48} _{-2.33}	+0.41 ^{+8.41} _{-5.62}	0.1 ^{+0.1} _{-0.0}	-1.7 ^{+0.5} _{-0.3}	0.94 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	144.6 ^{+3.6} _{-5.8}
HD2-N3	2017-09-07	-0.41 ^{+0.27} _{-0.23}	-0.12 ^{+0.15} _{-0.10}	8.7 ^{+13.5} _{-3.5}	-3.8 ^{+6.1} _{-1.4}	1.00 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	139.8 ^{+9.9} _{-10.6}
HD2-N4	2018-07-07	-0.17 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	-0.13 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	65.2 ^{+11.4} _{-10.8}	-10.5 ^{+7.3} _{-6.8}	0.96 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	144.3 ^{+9.9} _{-9.9}
HD2-N5	2018-08-29	-0.26 ^{+0.08} _{-0.11}	-0.27 ^{+0.12} _{-0.16}	20.6 ^{+12.7} _{-8.4}	-4.1 ^{+2.3} _{-3.5}	0.98 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	143.4 ^{+10.1} _{-10.0}
HD2-N6	2018-09-05	-0.25 ^{+9.06} _{-7.49}	-0.66 ^{+6.01} _{-9.31}	0.2 ^{+0.2} _{-14.8}	+3.7 ^{+7.7} _{-12.7}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	144.8 ^{+11.6} _{-10.6}
HD2-N7	2019-08-27	-0.29 ^{+0.10} _{-0.14}	-0.12 ^{+0.08} _{-0.10}	19.2 ^{+8.9} _{-10.1}	-6.7 ^{+4.0} _{-3.2}	1.00 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	145.1 ^{+10.4} _{-10.3}
HD2-N8	2019-09-03	-0.29 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	-0.12 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	24.7 ^{+5.3} _{-4.2}	-10.6 ^{+2.4} _{-2.5}	1.00 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	140.9 ^{+9.9} _{-9.9}
All nights		-0.16 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	-0.15 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	30.1 ^{+7.1} _{-5.8}	-1.5 ^{+1.8} _{-1.6}	0.99 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	137.7 ^{+10.4} _{-10.0}
HD2-N5+N7+N8		-0.26 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	-0.13 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	26.2 ^{+4.4} _{-3.9}	-8.6 ^{+1.9} _{-2.0}	0.99 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	139.0 ^{+9.6} _{-9.6}

 Table B.8: Summary of the best-fit parameters and $1-\sigma$ error bars obtained with the MCMC fitting procedure for WASP-80 b.

WASP-80 b							
		$c D_2$	$c D_1$	FWHM	v_{wind}	r	K_p
		[%]	[%]	[km s ⁻¹]	[km s ⁻¹]	[R _p]	[km s ⁻¹]
W80-N1	2019-08-09	-1.57 ^{+4.78} _{-8.05}	+0.74 ^{+7.80} _{-5.44}	4.0 ^{+7.6} _{-3.4}	-5.9 ^{+10.5} _{-4.2}	0.93 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	124.2 ^{+9.9} _{-12.2}
W80-N2	2019-09-21	+3.60 ^{+1.38} _{-1.17}	+3.91 ^{+1.09} _{-1.05}	10.2 ^{+2.4} _{-2.2}	-4.8 ^{+1.2} _{-1.3}	0.97 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	116.9 ^{+10.0} _{-9.7}
W80-N3	2020-06-26	-4.18 ^{+0.78} _{-0.83}	-4.21 ^{+1.05} _{-1.09}	29.9 ^{+7.3} _{-5.4}	+3.1 ^{+2.1} _{-2.6}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	110.2 ^{+10.4} _{-10.4}
W80-N4	2021-08-02	+11.0 ^{+2.8} _{-2.7}	+3.73 ^{+2.39} _{-2.15}	11.1 ^{+2.5} _{-2.2}	-7.4 ^{+1.2} _{-1.3}	0.97 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	116.4 ^{+9.5} _{-9.6}
W80-N5	2022-07-30	+1.59 ^{+7.10} _{-5.44}	-7.63 ^{+8.16} _{-7.46}	1.3 ^{+2.6} _{-0.9}	-20.6 ^{+25.1} _{-1.2}	0.96 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	114.9 ^{+12.0} _{-8.2}
W80-N6	2023-06-17	-3.80 ^{+1.65} _{-1.82}	-6.89 ^{+1.78} _{-1.95}	8.1 ^{+2.1} _{-1.7}	-1.1 ^{+1.0} _{-1.1}	0.89 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	117.0 ^{+9.9} _{-10.0}
W80-N7	2023-09-08	+5.10 ^{+8.96} _{-2.56}	-0.15 ^{+1.57} _{-2.89}	17.4 ^{+26.2} _{-15.5}	-0.1 ^{+6.5} _{-13.8}	0.97 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	119.8 ^{+9.4} _{-10.3}
All nights		-0.58 ^{+0.55} _{-0.61}	-1.58 ^{+0.61} _{-0.54}	12.2 ^{+4.0} _{-5.7}	+7.7 ^{+4.0} _{-3.2}	0.84 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	117.9 ^{+10.8} _{-10.5}
W80-N6		-3.73 ^{+1.65} _{-1.81}	-6.84 ^{+1.88} _{-1.92}	8.2 ^{+2.2} _{-1.8}	-1.1 ^{+1.0} _{-1.1}	0.89 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	117.5 ^{+9.8} _{-10.0}

 Table B.9: Summary of the best-fit parameters and $1-\sigma$ error bars obtained with the MCMC fitting procedure for WASP-127 b.

WASP-127 b							
		$c D_2$	$c D_1$	FWHM	v_{wind}	r	K_p
		[%]	[%]	[km s ⁻¹]	[km s ⁻¹]	[R _p]	[km s ⁻¹]
N1	2017-02-27	-0.32 ^{+0.12} _{-0.24}	-0.30 ^{+0.12} _{-0.21}	47.7 ^{+37.7} _{-21.7}	+0.7 ^{+6.7} _{-6.5}	1.01 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	129.9 ^{+10.2} _{-9.7}
N2	2017-03-20	-0.72 ^{+0.56} _{-5.01}	-0.76 ^{+0.58} _{-4.83}	2.4 ^{+22.4} _{-2.3}	-6.6 ^{+13.3} _{-5.5}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	133.6 ^{+9.1} _{-12.1}
N3	2018-03-31	-0.14 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}	-0.29 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}	91.6 ^{+6.4} _{-18.1}	+18.5 ^{+4.8} _{-11.9}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	129.8 ^{+8.7} _{-9.5}
N4	2019-02-20	-0.49 ^{+0.18} _{-1.85}	-0.09 ^{+0.07} _{-2.29}	57.5 ^{+30.9} _{-57.2}	-4.0 ^{+14.3} _{-14.6}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.04}	129.9 ^{+10.3} _{-10.4}
N5	2021-02-16	-0.75 ^{+0.41} _{-6.75}	-0.28 ^{+0.23} _{-6.97}	9.8 ^{+69.6} _{-9.7}	+11.0 ^{+10.2} _{-15.7}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	130.1 ^{+9.9} _{-10.3}
N6	2022-02-27	-1.08 ^{+0.24} _{-0.29}	-0.26 ^{+0.14} _{-0.17}	31.6 ^{+7.8} _{-7.1}	+9.7 ^{+3.4} _{-2.6}	0.99 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	117.0 ^{+10.8} _{-10.9}
All nights		-0.18 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	-0.17 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	91.0 ^{+6.6} _{-11.6}	+18.0 ^{+4.6} _{-6.0}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	129.6 ^{+9.8} _{-10.3}
W127-N1+N2+N6		-0.52 ^{+0.13} _{-0.15}	-0.36 ^{+0.10} _{-0.11}	30.2 ^{+6.9} _{-5.8}	+1.5 ^{+3.0} _{-2.5}	1.00 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	125.8 ^{+10.1} _{-10.6}

Fig. B.2: As Fig. 6 but for WASP-80 b combining all nights analysed. For graphic purposes only, we fixed the D₂ line contrast of the Gaussian fit at zero being compatible with scatter.

Fig. B.3: *Top panel*: Master-out in the region of the Na I doublet for each night analysed of WASP-80 b. *Bottom panel*: Relative variation from the reference average profile, obtained by combining all nights.